

Appendix D

Hydroelectric Potential General Exhibits

LIST OF EXHIBITS

<u>EXHIBIT TITLE</u>	<u>EXHIBIT NUMBER</u>
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - GENERAL SITE MAP	D-1
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 1 OF 7	D-2
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 2 OF 7	D-3
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 3 OF 7	D-4
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 4 OF 7	D-5
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 5 OF 7	D-6
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 6 OF 7	D-7
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 7 OF 7	D-8
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - GENERAL SUMMARY TABLE 1 OF 3	D-9-1
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - GENERAL SUMMARY TABLE 2 OF 3	D-9-2
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - GENERAL SUMMARY TABLE 3 OF 3	D-9-3
HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - GENERAL SITES COORDINATES	D-10

OVERVIEW MAP PANELS

PANEL 1 - SITES LIST

Site ID	Site Name	Power Max. KW	Power Avg. KW	Power Min. KW	Annual Energy KWH
HTGA-01	Grande_Anse_#1	6099	4769	2364	41,776,509.47
HTGA-02	Grande_Anse_#2	4703	4025	2817	35,258,775.34
HTGA-03	Grande_Anse_#3	1400	1087	683	9,518,899.69
HTGA-04	Grande_Anse_#4	1261	1175	1028	10,293,385.17
HTGA-05	Riviere_de_la_Voldrogue	2664	2017	1336	17,672,987.97
HTGA-06	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#1	4204	3301	1776	28,915,169.44
HTGA-07	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#2	3557	2763	1527	24,207,545.47
HTGA-08	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#3	2484	1506	847	13,189,179.78
HTGA-09	Riviere_Glace_#1	1482	863	464	7,556,360.61
HTGA-10	Riviere_Glace_#2	1448	868	476	7,603,703.25
HTGA-11	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#1	4070	2625	1346	22,992,425.57
HTGA-12	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#2	2966	1924	1007	16,853,511.39
HTGA-13	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#3	428	282	148	2,473,342.26
HTNP-04	Riviere_des_Barraderes	91	60	31	523,443.34
HTSD-01	Ravine_du_Sud	2569	1778	643	15,571,162.54
HTSD-02	Riviere_Acul	1914	1321	457	11,575,530.94
HTSD-03	Riviere_Cavaillon	528	353	130	3,090,235.02
HTSD-04	Riviere_Cavaillon_(existing)	2281	1194	599	10,458,147.50
HTSD-06	Riviere_des_Anglais_#1	1007	717	289	6,284,839.49
HTSD-07	Riviere_des_Anglais_#2	1308	921	372	8,071,174.38
HTSD-08	Riviere_Mombin	204	95	27	832,451.65
HTSD-09	Riviere_Mulet	569	302	107	2,646,059.25
HTSD-10	Riviere_Port_a_Piment	916	643	247	5,635,626.00

LEGEND

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 - Pico (P < 50 KW)
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HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 1 OF 7

OVERVIEW MAP PANELS

PANEL 2 - SITES LIST

Site ID	Site Name	Power Max. KW	Power Avg. KW	Power Min. KW	Annual Energy KWH
HTNP-01	Grande Riviere_de_Nippes_#1	2779	2566	2263	22,480,001.96
HTNP-02	Grande Riviere_de_Nippes_#2	3268	2776	2052	24,318,129.64
HTNP-03	Riviere_Charlier	121	59	25	517,028.38
HTNP-05	Riviere_Saut_du_Baril	175	98	51	857,903.33
HTOT-01	Etang_de_Miragoane	70	67	58	585,076.98
HTOT-09	Riviere_Barret	100	51	20	442,470.11
HTOT-16	Riviere_Fauche	40	23	9	202,000.70
HTOT-29	Riviere_Amazones_#2	425	256	60	2,240,509.61
HTSD-05	Riviere_Cotes_de_Fer	154	153	148	1,342,757.95
HTSD-11	Riviere_Millionnaire	437	219	76	1,914,782.00
HTSE-02	Petite Riviere_de_Jacmel_#2	199	85	25	745,677.31
HTSE-03	Riviere_Amazones_#1	421	259	69	2,273,046.90
HTSE-05	Riviere_Bainet_#1	1841	1182	383	10,351,643.22
HTSE-06	Riviere_Bainet_#2	1049	649	194	5,688,154.86
HTSE-08	Riviere_Dlo_Gene	33	15	4	127,441.81
HTSE-12	Riviere_Jacmel_Bras_Gauche	747	555	200	4,860,824.14
HTSE-14	Riviere_Linet_#1	563	247	58	2,161,099.29
HTSE-15	Riviere_Linet_#2	351	167	39	1,458,958.51
HTSE-16	Riviere_Madame_Louis	317	160	64	1,405,785.74
HTSE-19	Riviere_Ti_Letan	974	462	115	4,043,198.75
HTSE-20	Riviere_Zoranger	683	352	95	3,083,415.36

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HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 2 OF 7

OVERVIEW MAP PANELS

PANEL 3 - SITES LIST

Site ID	Site Name	Power Max. KW	Power Avg. KW	Power Min. KW	Annual Energy KWH
HTOT-03	Ravine_Grande	414	293	177	2,563,014.75
HTOT-04	Ravine_Minerve	381	271	167	2,375,976.93
HTOT-07	Riviere_au_Foure_(Momance)	467	326	113	2,853,935.64
HTOT-10	Riviere_Blanche_Ouest_#1	1030	815	574	7,136,044.53
HTOT-11	Riviere_Blanche_Ouest_#2	1215	960	677	8,407,784.59
HTOT-12	Riviere_Boucan_Greffin	957	703	461	6,161,945.32
HTOT-17	Riviere_Fond_Parisien_#1	1711	1268	855	11,105,928.72
HTOT-18	Riviere_Fond_Parisien_#2	345	238	149	2,081,407.07
HTOT-19	Riviere_Froide	1310	809	328	7,090,739.68
HTOT-20	Ravine_Eau_Fatiguee	398	301	191	2,636,379.29
HTOT-23	Riviere_Momance_#1	2977	2072	771	18,151,407.19
HTOT-24	Riviere_Momance_#2	5179	3407	1457	29,849,591.91
HTOT-25	Riviere_Momance_#3	827	515	219	4,512,061.41
HTOT-27	Riviere_Redoute	287	191	98	1,671,761.00
HTOT-28	Riviere_Soliete	1558	660	166	5,777,607.09
HTOT-30	Riviere_Grise_#1	2798	2189	1229	19,176,695.51
HTOT-31	Riviere_Grise_#2	1476	1204	611	10,550,029.31
HTOT-32	Riviere_Grise_#3	1120	994	644	8,710,226.84
HTSE-01	Pette_Riviere_de_Jacmel_#1	143	62	17	542,423.61
HTSE-04	Riviere_Panide	795	385	89	3,369,803.24
HTSE-07	Ravine_Perduline	5966	2824	731	24,740,616.48
HTSE-09	Riviere_Gaillard	113	46	11	402,927.86
HTSE-10	Riviere_Gaillard_(existing)	637	366	193	3,206,625.03
HTSE-11	Riviere_Jacmel_Bras_Droit	335	270	137	2,363,199.37
HTSE-13	Riviere_la_Gosseline	699	346	128	3,032,399.17
HTSE-17	Riviere_des_Plantils	521	254	73	2,227,304.30
HTSE-18	Riviere_Pichon	4098	1907	466	16,707,298.79
HTSE-21	Ravine_Loquette	1529	781	179	6,838,359.17

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HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 3 OF 7

-73°30'0.000"

-73°0'0.000"

19°0'0.000"

19°0'0.000"

-73°30'0.000"

-73°0'0.000"

OVERVIEW MAP PANELS

PANEL 4 - SITES LIST

Site ID	Site Name	Power Max. KW	Power Avg. KW	Power Min. KW	Annual Energy KWH
HTAR-01	Deluge-Lanzac_(existing)	1122	765	390	6,703,802.01
HTAR-02	Drouet_(existing)	1373	755	343	6,612,046.80
HTAR-16	Riviere_Montrouis_#1	437	258	38	2,261,158.33
HTAR-17	Riviere_Montrouis_#2	426	227	54	1,988,479.37
HTAR-18	Riviere_Montrouis_#3	69	35	9	308,808.77
HTAR-19	Riviere_Montrouis_#4	146	83	24	723,269.72
HTAR-20	Riviere_Montrouis_#5	121	67	19	584,141.95
HTAR-21	Riviere_Montrouis_#6	58	29	8	258,417.85

GULF OF GONAVE

PORT-AU-PRINCE BAY

LEGEND

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HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 4 OF 7

EXHIBIT D-5

OVERVIEW MAP PANELS

PANEL 5 - SITES LIST

Site ID	Site Name	Power Max. KW	Power Avg. KW	Power Min. KW	Annual Energy KWH
HTAR-04	Ravine_Montas	98	41	6	355,996.49
HTAR-05	Riviere_Blanche	107	40	4	352,688.32
HTAR-06	Riviere_Boucan_Fete	141	73	20	639,157.46
HTAR-07	Riviere_Bouillie_#1	1003	700	316	6,127,762.28
HTAR-08	Riviere_Bouillie_#2	183	91	22	797,930.66
HTAR-09	Riviere_Bouillie_#3	1015	659	325	5,773,407.23
HTAR-10	Riviere_Cabeuil	411	193	54	1,688,291.24
HTAR-11	Riviere_Deco	255	155	62	1,358,091.94
HTAR-13	Riviere_Estere_#1	283	128	30	1,120,386.48
HTAR-14	Riviere_Estere_#2	426	219	72	1,918,918.03
HTAR-15	Riviere_Monorouge	137	71	23	625,477.75
HTAR-22	Riviere_Mory	285	163	59	1,429,939.64
HTAR-23	Riviere_Roche	102	41	6	359,911.69
HTAR-24	Riviere_Tapion_#1	342	200	71	1,753,602.44
HTAR-25	Riviere_Tapion_#2	31	17	4	145,293.65
HTAR-26	Riviere_Rio_Belle	109	85	50	742,604.75
HTAR-27	EDH_ART-1	25940	17399	6413	152,417,345.54
HTAR-28	EDH_ART-2	40066	26932	9915	235,923,906.90
HTAR-29	Riviere_Zepelin	58	30	9	266,273.78
HTCT-01	EDH_ART-4C	19207	11249	2114	98,539,495.00
HTCT-02	EDH_Peligre_(existing)	47040	35089	18822	307,377,106.28
HTCT-03	EDH_Dos_Bocas	39972	32557	22175	285,203,025.29
HTCT-04	EDH_GU-1	10358	9414	7846	82,463,829.60
HTCT-05	Onde_Verde_(existing)	342	260	138	2,281,411.41
HTCT-06	Ravine_Trou_Enfer	87	32	4	280,001.98
HTCT-07	Riviere_Abrio	69	27	4	234,637.23
HTCT-08	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#1	213	182	137	1,595,849.80
HTCT-09	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#2	153	60	7	528,012.99
HTCT-10	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#3	595	266	47	2,330,745.78
HTCT-11	Riviere_Cabourette	64	25	5	221,981.95
HTCT-12	Riviere_de_Lascaobas	120	87	49	764,792.09
HTCT-13	Riviere_de_Thomonde	836	358	66	3,132,482.08
HTCT-14	Riviere_des_Capucins	265	107	12	937,554.61
HTCT-15	Riviere_Dos_Roye	22	9	3	80,876.23
HTCT-16	Riviere_Fond_Bleu_#1	247	97	16	853,537.43
HTCT-17	Riviere_Fond_Bleu_#2	334	148	22	1,294,294.63
HTCT-18	Riviere_Fond_Gras	635	279	43	2,442,990.72
HTCT-19	Riviere_Fraicheur	33	23	13	202,589.92
HTCT-20	Riviere_Grand_Saut	629	289	70	2,535,142.06
HTCT-21	Riviere_Hinquette	102	40	7	353,904.69
HTCT-22	Riviere_la_Theme_#1	947	634	161	5,557,435.92
HTCT-23	Riviere_la_Theme_#2	318	144	30	1,259,130.58
HTCT-24	Riviere_Layaye	340	227	58	1,992,704.90
HTCT-25	Riviere_Goyave	10	4	1	33,282.22
HTCT-26	Riviere_Rio_Frio	323	135	15	1,180,301.40
HTCT-27	Riviere_Roche_Blanche	510	427	235	3,741,516.68

LEGEND

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Cities

- Major Cities
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- Capital

Minor Cities

- Roads
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HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 5 OF 7

PANEL 6 - SITES LIST

Site ID	Site Name	Power Max. KW	Power Avg. KW	Power Min. KW	Annual Energy KWH
HTAR-03	EDH_TR-78	1871	1617	1106	14,164,924.08
HTNO-01	EDH_TR-28	3328	2120	397	18,569,875.18
HTNO-02	Riviere_au_Four	74	36	12	318,584.81
HTNO-03	Riviere_Bon_Temps	115	66	24	578,227.48
HTNO-04	Riviere_Cap_Rouge	54	25	9	220,927.99
HTNO-05	Riviere_Dejour	88	42	13	364,412.38
HTNO-06	Riviere_des_Barres_#1	500	291	138	2,552,105.60
HTNO-07	Riviere_des_Barres_#2	105	67	31	587,417.46
HTNO-08	Riviere_des_Barres_#3	41	22	9	188,855.49
HTNO-09	Riviere_des_Barres_#4	168	88	30	773,926.96
HTNO-10	Riviere_Dlo_Biolel	77	42	18	369,579.56
HTNO-11	Riviere_Mapou	60	27	9	240,093.76
HTNO-12	Riviere_Sainte_Anne	81	36	11	314,127.78
HTNO-13	Riviere_Zombi	50	28	11	247,728.44
HTNO-14	Riviere_des_Barres_#5	321	185	65	1,618,613.51

LEGEND

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Cities

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Roads

Departements

Water Bodies

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Watersheds

HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 6 OF 7

EXHIBIT D-7

ATLANTIC OCEAN

OVERVIEW MAP PANELS

PANEL 7 - SITES LIST

Site ID	Site Name	Power Max. KW	Power Avg. KW	Power Min. KW	Annual Energy KWH
HTAR-12	Riviere_Ennery	145	84	26	739,543.10
HTND-01	Grande_Ravine	857	504	170	4,416,118.55
HTND-02	Petite_Riviere	514	307	111	2,693,455.23
HTND-03	Riviere_Bouyaha	118	76	30	665,268.10
HTND-04	Riviere_Caracol_(existing)	696	432	160	3,780,215.40
HTND-05	Riviere_Dore	502	311	112	2,723,757.32
HTND-06	Riviere_Marmelade	637	388	133	3,399,736.02
HTND-07	Riviere_Morro_#1	325	319	298	2,794,131.09
HTND-08	Riviere_Morro_#2	228	128	48	1,124,462.91
HTND-09	Riviere_Vaseuse	16	9	3	79,703.76
HTNE-01	Grande_Riviere_du_Nord_#1	863	589	198	5,159,935.71
HTNE-02	Grande_Riviere_du_Nord_#2	1720	1167	371	10,221,853.59
HTNE-03	Riviere_Marrion	184	172	126	1,505,770.00
HTNE-04	Riviere_Louisa	115	72	21	630,978.84
HTNE-05	Riviere_Gens_de_Nantes_#1	146	117	53	1,024,317.94
HTNE-06	Riviere_Gens_de_Nantes_#2	285	167	50	1,462,898.90

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HAITI - HYDROELECTRIC POTENTIAL - PANEL 7 OF 7

EXHIBIT D-8

SITE ID	SITE DEPARTEMENT	SITE NAME	DAM W.S. EL. (m)	POWER HOUSE T.W. EL. (m)	GROSS HEAD (m)	TURBINE FLOW (cms)	PENSTOCK DIAMETER (m)	PENSTOCK LENGTH (m)	CANAL WIDTH (m)	CANAL LENGTH (m)	TURBINE TYPE	AMOUNT OF TURBINES	JANUARY POWER (KW)	FEBRUARY POWER (KW)	MARCH POWER (KW)	APRIL POWER (KW)	MAY POWER (KW)	JUNE POWER (KW)	JULY POWER (KW)	AUGUST POWER (KW)	SEPTEMBER POWER (KW)	OCTOBER POWER (KW)	NOVEMBER POWER (KW)	DECEMBER POWER (KW)	MAXIMUM POWER (KW)	AVERAGE POWER (KW)	MINIMUM POWER (KW)	YEARLY ENERGY PRODUCTION (KWH)	SITE CLASSIFICATION	
HTAR-01	Artibonite	Deluge-Lanzac_(existing)	380.33	84.02	296.31	0.579	0.457	2000	0.00	0	Pelton	2	735	619	484	390	597	766	461	872	1106	1106	1040	889	1122	765	390	6,703,802	Small	
HTAR-02	Artibonite	Drouet_(existing)	29.00	20.00	2.54	22.793	2.438	5	0.00	0	Ossberger	5	657	530	425	343	763	758	453	525	1259	1373	987	805	1373	755	343	6,612,047	Small	
HTAR-03	Artibonite	EDH_TR-78	270.00	234.33	35.67	7.197	1.829	1615	0.00	0	Francis	2	1484	1428	1106	1378	1761	1754	1537	1672	1754	1754	1754	1828	1871	1617	1106	14,164,924	Macro	
HTAR-04	Artibonite	Ravine_Montas	283.17	214.28	68.89	0.198	0.457	2227	0.75	1113	Pelton	1	14	10	6	13	15	49	28	63	98	98	55	29	98	41	6	355,996	Pico	
HTAR-05	Artibonite	Riviere_Blanche	250.80	176.69	74.11	0.204	0.457	1192	0.75	596	Mitchell	1	13	9	4	10	14	45	25	65	107	107	53	26	107	40	4	352,688	Pico	
HTAR-06	Artibonite	Riviere_Boucan_Fete	443.21	305.48	137.73	0.131	0.381	1584	0.50	792	Pelton	1	34	29	20	36	49	90	71	117	141	141	85	53	141	73	20	639,157	Micro	
HTAR-07	Artibonite	Riviere_Bouillie_#1	155.93	93.85	62.08	2.403	1.219	2257	2.25	1128	Mitchell	2	383	391	316	596	820	880	815	898	1003	1003	710	537	1003	700	316	6,127,762	Small	
HTAR-08	Artibonite	Riviere_Bouillie_#2	421.41	151.17	270.24	0.088	0.305	2464	0.50	1232	Pelton	1	41	34	22	42	54	112	86	147	183	183	108	66	183	91	22	797,931	Micro	
HTAR-09	Artibonite	Riviere_Bouillie_#3	392.75	200.12	192.63	0.727	0.610	2106	1.25	1053	Pelton	1	374	341	325	390	577	853	814	912	1003	1015	719	502	1015	659	325	5,773,407	Small	
HTAR-10	Artibonite	Riviere_Cabeuil	311.05	51.88	259.17	0.244	0.457	6288	0.75	3144	Mitchell	1	95	81	54	93	134	256	120	232	411	410	247	149	411	193	54	1,688,291	Mini	
HTAR-11	Artibonite	Riviere_Deco	212.96	122.52	90.44	0.377	0.610	2680	1.00	1340	Pelton	1	82	78	62	125	143	183	158	217	255	255	173	118	255	155	62	1,358,092	Mini	
HTAR-12	Artibonite	Riviere_Ennery	284.00	259.36	24.64	0.903	0.914	1632	1.50	816	Mitchell	1	56	44	26	36	74	116	65	84	133	145	141	84	145	84	26	739,543	Micro	
HTAR-13	Artibonite	Riviere_Estere_#1	119.27	63.71	55.56	0.757	0.914	4098	1.25	2049	Mitchell	1	51	44	30	64	103	165	89	177	283	283	144	83	283	128	30	1,120,386	Mini	
HTAR-14	Artibonite	Riviere_Estere_#2	218.76	124.77	93.99	0.633	0.762	5091	1.25	2545	Pelton	2	114	100	72	134	172	272	160	294	419	419	259	172	426	219	72	1,918,918	Mini	
HTAR-15	Artibonite	Riviere_Monrouge	416.80	227.55	189.25	0.093	0.305	1544	0.50	772	Pelton	1	41	35	23	36	48	90	51	96	137	137	90	61	137	71	23	625,478	Micro	
HTAR-16	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouais_#1	210.41	188.92	21.49	2.638	1.372	973	2.50	487	Kaplan	2	61	59	38	232	355	363	298	409	437	437	275	105	437	258	38	2,261,158	Mini	
HTAR-17	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouais_#2	555.85	468.22	87.63	0.741	0.762	3265	1.25	1633	Mitchell	1	99	84	54	120	188	276	225	356	426	426	286	160	426	227	54	1,988,479	Mini	
HTAR-18	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouais_#3	431.96	369.21	62.75	0.160	0.381	855	0.75	427	Mitchell	1	17	14	9	15	22	41	33	55	68	69	47	29	69	35	9	308,809	Pico	
HTAR-19	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouais_#4	619.52	465.07	154.45	0.132	0.305	1385	0.75	692	Pelton	1	47	38	24	40	57	96	81	124	145	146	110	72	146	83	24	723,270	Micro	
HTAR-20	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouais_#5	561.92	445.62	116.30	0.136	0.381	1568	0.75	784	Pelton	1	37	30	19	31	45	77	64	100	120	121	89	57	121	67	19	584,142	Micro	
HTAR-21	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouais_#6	572.06	413.57	158.49	0.046	0.305	1739	0.50	869	Pelton	1	16	13	8	14	16	32	26	45	57	58	40	25	58	29	8	258,418	Pico	
HTAR-22	Artibonite	Riviere_Mory	243.57	107.46	136.11	0.274	0.533	2974	0.75	1487	Pelton	1	83	77	59	116	135	194	164	238	285	285	185	123	285	163	59	1,429,940	Mini	
HTAR-23	Artibonite	Riviere_Roche	293.69	93.28	200.41	0.065	0.305	2494	0.50	1247	Pelton	1	15	11	6	11	15	49	26	64	102	102	56	29	102	41	6	359,912	Pico	
HTAR-24	Artibonite	Riviere_Tapion_#1	282.31	196.34	85.97	0.561	0.762	2663	1.25	1331	Mitchell	1	99	94	71	147	190	244	212	283	342	342	220	144	342	200	71	1,753,602	Mini	
HTAR-25	Artibonite	Riviere_Tapion_#2	368.78	322.63	46.15	0.096	0.305	807	0.50	404	Pelton	1	8	7	4	8	10	21	16	26	31	31	20	13	31	17	4	145,294	Pico	
HTAR-26	Centre	Riviere_Rio_Belle	350.00	323.92	26.08	0.541	0.762	1362	0.00	0	Kaplan	2	57	55	50	63	109	109	82	101	109	109	90	68	109	85	50	742,605	Micro	
HTAR-27	Artibonite	EDH_ART-1	50.00	29.72	20.28	159.143	6.706	71	0.00	0	Kaplan	4	6849	7279	6413	16037	25940	25844	17594	24606	25940	25940	15364	9147	25940	17399	6413	152,417,346	Large	
HTAR-28	Artibonite	EDH_ART-2	90.00	56.50	33.50	146.244	6.096	46	0.00	0	Kaplan	3	10757	11345	9915	24379	40066	39554	26496	37148	40066	40066	23597	14613	40066	26932	9915	235,923,907	Large	
HTAR-29	Artibonite	Riviere_Zepelin	263.37	177.99	85.38	0.095	0.305	1573	0.00	0	Pelton	1	14	12	9	17	21	37	29	47	58	58	36	22	58	30	9	266,274	Pico	
HTCT-01	Centre	EDH_ART-4C	115.00	92.00	23.00	112.199	6.401	90	8.00	3400	Francis	3	2319	2646	2114	9777	18016	18016	11118	17682	18016	18016	8339	3922	19207	11249	2114	98,539,495	Large	
HTCT-02	Centre	EDH_Peligre_(existing)	172.00	118.60	44.57	123.000	3.810	94	0.00	0	Francis	3	20828	18822	19104	26576	44120	44120	43878	44120	44120	44120	38750	22628	47040	35089	18822	307,377,106	Large	
HTCT-03	Centre	EDH_Dos_Bocas	220.00	171.69	48.31	106.124	5.182	1115	0.00	0	Francis	3	22467	23336	22175	31742	37492	37492	38713	37492	37492	37492	34488	25938	39972	32557	22175	285,203,025	Large	
HTCT-04	Centre	EDH_GU-1	220.00	176.02	43.98	31.462	3.048	1137	0.00	0	Francis	2	8660	8474	7846	9766	9751	9751	9751	9751	9751	9751	9751	9751	9675	10358	9414	7846	82,463,830	Macro
HTCT-05	Centre	Onde_Verde_(existing)	346.15	326.40	19.75	2.356	0.914	50	0.00	0	Ossberger	1	173	138	146	283	339	253	279	327	294	342	297	216	342	260	138	2,281,411	Mini	
HTCT-06	Centre	Ravine_Trou_Enfer	293.59	264.37	29.22	0.438	0.610	702	1.50	351	Mitchell	1	11	8	4	10	13	36	15	43	87	87	44	21	87	32	4	280,002	Pico	
HTCT-07	Centre	Riviere_Abrio	454.27	352.99	101.28	0.088	0.381	2501	0.50	1251	Pelton	1	11	8	4	7	11	32	12	34	69	69	39	20	69	27	4	234,637	Pico	
HTCT-08	Centre	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#1	220.00	192.82	27.18	1.100	0.610	155	0.00	0	Francis	2	158	149	137	156	173	200	194	200	200	200	200	188	213	182	137	1,595,850	Mini	
HTCT-09	Centre	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#2	292.39	266.85	25.54	0.860	0.914	1057	1.25	528	Mitchell	1	20	14	7	15	31	73	37	94	153	153	79	39	153	60	7	528,013	Micro	
HTCT-10	Centre	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#3	422.59	320.52	102.07	0.773	0.762	2600	1.25	1300	Pelton	2	110	82	47	82	171	330	190	410	586	586	349	196	595	266	47	2,330,746	Mini	
HTCT-11	Centre	Riviere_Cabourette	771.60	659.91	111.69	0.075	0.305	1665	0.50	833	Pelton	1	14	11	8	15	21	11	5	22	59	64	42	24	64	25	5	221,982	Pico	
HTCT-12	Centre	Riviere_de_Lascaobas	434.04	330.13	103.91	0.150	0.381	1154	0.75	577	Pelton	1	54	54	49	96	101	93	82	100	118	120	102	72	120	87	49	764,792	Micro	
HTCT-13	Centre	Riviere_de_Thomonde	507.17	350.32	156.85	0.720	0.762	5366	1.50	2683	Pelton	2	151	114	66	121	216	426	202	507	823	823	489	269	836	358	66	3,132,482	Mini	
HTCT-14	Centre	Riviere_des_Capucins	130.79	98.27	32.52	1.251	1.067	2532	1.50	1266	Mitchell	1	33	23	12	34	48	135	80	172	265	265	133	65	265	107	12	937,555	Mini	
HTCT-15	Centre	Riviere_Dos_Roye	616.48	554.45	62.03	0.047	0.305	1564	0.50	782	Pelton	1	4	4	3	8	10	5	3	8	19	22	15	7	22	9	3	80,876	Pico	
HTCT-16	Centre	Riviere_Fond_Bleu_#1	390.00	315.37	74.63	0.463	0.762	2806	1.00	1403	Mitchell	1	37	27	16	26	47	129	51	130	247	247	130	65	247	97	16	853,537	Micro	
HTCT-17	Centre	Riviere_Fond_Bleu_#2	526.45	396.91	129.54	0.367	0.533	3226	1.00	1613	Pelton	1	60	43	22	39	80	204	87	215	334	334	207	112	334	148				

SITE ID	SITE DEPARTEMENT	SITE NAME	DAM W.S. EL. (m)	POWER HOUSE T.W. EL. (m)	GROSS HEAD (m)	TURBINE FLOW (cms)	PENSTOCK DIAMETER (m)	PENSTOCK LENGTH (m)	CANAL WIDTH (m)	CANAL LENGTH (m)	TURBINE TYPE	AMOUNT OF TURBINES	JANUARY POWER (KW)	FEBRUARY POWER (KW)	MARCH POWER (KW)	APRIL POWER (KW)	MAY POWER (KW)	JUNE POWER (KW)	JULY POWER (KW)	AUGUST POWER (KW)	SEPTEMBER POWER (KW)	OCTOBER POWER (KW)	NOVEMBER POWER (KW)	DECEMBER POWER (KW)	MAXIMUM POWER (KW)	AVERAGE POWER (KW)	MINIMUM POWER (KW)	YEARLY ENERGY PRODUCTION (KWH)	SITE CLASSIFICATION	
HTGA-04	Grande Anse	Grande_Anse_#4	190.00	145.09	44.91	3.700	0.914	110	0.00	0	Francis	3	1183	1189	1028	1217	1183	1183	1135	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1261	1175	1028	10,293,385	Macro	
HTGA-05	Grande Anse	Riviere_de_la_Voldrogue	130.00	66.55	63.45	5.965	1.524	1693	4.00	847	Pelton	2	1939	1719	1336	1593	2519	1984	1498	1817	2133	2623	2623	2111	2664	2017	1336	17,672,988	Macro	
HTGA-06	Grande Anse	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#1	110.00	36.97	73.03	7.353	1.981	2837	0.00	0	Francis	3	3280	2889	1776	2736	3959	3391	2267	3266	3964	3959	3959	3372	4204	3301	1776	28,915,169	Macro	
HTGA-07	Grande Anse	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#2	259.75	149.28	110.47	4.315	1.524	4765	3.00	2382	Francis	3	2755	2420	1588	2049	3339	2878	2006	2714	3281	3339	3339	2928	3557	2763	1527	24,207,545	Macro	
HTGA-08	Grande Anse	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#3	517.29	304.55	212.74	1.614	0.762	1743	2.00	871	Pelton	2	1467	1275	847	960	1831	1329	922	1164	1504	2465	2444	1681	2484	1506	847	13,189,180	Macro	
HTGA-09	Grande Anse	Riviere_Glace_#1	557.67	427.77	129.90	1.458	0.914	2619	0.00	0	Pelton	2	808	702	464	535	1032	756	519	679	872	1472	1472	944	1482	863	464	7,556,361	Small	
HTGA-10	Grande Anse	Riviere_Glace_#2	712.80	562.62	150.18	1.302	0.762	2793	0.00	0	Pelton	2	818	715	476	547	1040	777	537	700	889	1429	1429	954	1448	868	476	7,603,703	Small	
HTGA-11	Grande Anse	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#1	490.38	300.39	189.99	2.876	1.219	4243	2.50	2121	Pelton	1	2276	2018	1346	1692	3332	2590	1819	2357	2986	4070	4070	2668	4070	2625	1346	22,992,426	Macro	
HTGA-12	Grande Anse	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#2	916.28	546.54	369.74	1.050	0.762	4477	1.50	2238	Pelton	2	1635	1469	1007	1237	2398	1933	1408	1754	2232	2932	2932	1967	2966	1924	1007	16,853,511	Macro	
HTGA-13	Grande Anse	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#3	708.00	547.51	160.49	0.370	0.533	3399	1.00	1699	Pelton	1	247	220	148	179	351	282	201	256	323	428	428	297	428	282	148	2,473,342	Mini	
HTND-01	Nord	Grande_Ravine	212.16	125.44	86.72	1.452	1.067	3837	2.00	1919	Mitchell	1	371	288	170	193	512	672	351	434	692	853	857	607	857	504	170	4,416,119	Small	
HTND-02	Nord	Petite_Riviere	244.84	57.34	187.50	0.363	0.457	1255	1.00	628	Pelton	1	312	241	135	111	288	403	209	153	359	425	514	497	514	307	111	2,693,455	Mini	
HTND-03	Nord	Riviere_Bouyaha	427.44	408.83	18.61	0.981	1.067	2320	1.50	1160	Mitchell	1	51	46	30	41	85	105	56	69	103	118	118	81	118	76	30	665,268	Micro	
HTND-04	Nord	Riviere_Caracol_(existing)	280.74	101.89	178.85	0.495	0.457	424	1.00	1709	Pelton	2	394	311	184	160	374	585	314	265	572	640	686	646	696	432	160	3,780,215	Mini	
HTND-05	Nord	Riviere_Dore	374.69	268.86	105.83	0.613	0.762	2637	1.25	1319	Pelton	1	249	194	114	112	335	407	222	272	407	495	502	386	502	311	112	2,723,757	Mini	
HTND-06	Nord	Riviere_Marmelade	484.66	272.54	212.12	0.406	0.533	3106	1.00	1553	Pelton	1	299	231	134	133	392	520	283	356	538	637	637	454	637	388	133	3,399,736	Mini	
HTND-07	Nord	Riviere_Morro_#1	40.00	13.40	26.60	1.625	0.762	153	2.00	76	Kaplan	1	324	324	298	306	324	324	302	299	324	324	324	324	324	325	319	298	2,794,131	Mini
HTND-08	Nord	Riviere_Morro_#2	125.73	54.72	71.01	0.447	0.762	2574	1.00	1287	Mitchell	2	116	87	48	48	137	149	82	94	152	204	228	175	228	128	48	1,124,463	Mini	
HTND-09	Nord	Riviere_Vaseuse	425.05	416.82	8.23	0.273	0.762	980	0.00	0	Mitchell	1	7	6	3	4	9	13	6	6	12	15	16	12	16	9	3	79,704	Pico	
HTNE-01	Nord-Est	Grande_Riviere_du_Nord_#1	190.51	149.73	40.78	2.810	1.524	3745	3.00	1872	Francis	2	487	388	198	199	529	810	507	540	810	810	810	757	863	589	198	5,159,936	Small	
HTNE-02	Nord-Est	Grande_Riviere_du_Nord_#2	302.88	192.99	109.89	2.037	1.219	5216	3.00	2608	Francis	2	988	789	397	371	1015	1613	1039	1020	1613	1613	1613	1570	1720	1167	371	10,221,854	Macro	
HTNE-03	Nord-Est	Riviere_Marrion	65.00	29.72	35.28	0.660	1.219	3500	1.25	0	Francis	1	172	159	126	134	184	184	174	170	184	184	184	184	184	184	172	126	1,505,770	Mini
HTNE-04	Nord-Est	Riviere_Louisa	278.37	139.61	138.76	0.111	0.305	1264	0.50	632	Pelton	1	59	45	25	21	64	102	54	59	105	115	115	95	115	72	21	630,979	Micro	
HTNE-05	Nord-Est	Riviere_Gens_de_Nantes_#1	130.00	91.01	38.99	0.509	0.762	1790	1.00	895	Francis	1	98	79	53	59	118	146	117	117	146	146	146	141	146	117	53	1,024,318	Mini	
HTNE-06	Nord-Est	Riviere_Gens_de_Nantes_#2	598.76	209.82	388.94	0.094	0.305	2742	0.50	1371	Pelton	1	131	102	55	50	169	225	114	121	235	285	285	216	285	167	50	1,462,899	Mini	
HTNO-01	Nord-Ouest	EDH_TR-28	90.00	57.02	32.98	13.099	2.743	2609	0.00	0	Francis	2	702	685	397	1503	3124	3124	1856	2655	3124	3124	3124	1499	3328	2120	397	18,569,875	Macro	
HTNO-02	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_au_Four	129.44	59.70	69.74	0.157	0.381	1129	1.00	564	Mitchell	1	30	22	12	12	30	42	19	22	48	73	74	48	74	36	12	318,585	Pico	
HTNO-03	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Bon_Temps	270.17	148.41	121.76	0.132	0.305	1075	0.50	537	Pelton	1	57	43	24	24	59	81	42	50	89	113	115	85	115	66	24	578,227	Micro	
HTNO-04	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Cap_Rouge	80.80	9.30	71.50	0.110	0.381	1943	0.50	972	Mitchell	1	28	21	11	10	23	24	11	9	20	37	54	48	54	25	9	220,928	Pico	
HTNO-05	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Dejour	107.86	28.25	79.61	0.161	0.457	2596	0.75	1298	Mitchell	1	33	24	13	13	33	47	21	24	55	88	88	54	88	42	13	364,412	Pico	
HTNO-06	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#1	50.00	9.91	40.09	1.807	1.372	3625	2.25	1812	Mitchell	2	275	220	138	167	301	312	184	195	304	436	500	398	500	291	138	2,552,106	Mini	
HTNO-07	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#2	60.85	49.69	11.16	1.267	1.067	733	1.50	366	Kaplan	2	66	53	31	37	63	75	44	46	74	104	105	97	105	67	31	587,417	Micro	
HTNO-08	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#3	107.70	63.08	44.62	0.127	0.381	1167	0.50	583	Pelton	1	22	17	9	9	19	23	12	9	23	37	41	34	41	22	9	188,855	Pico	
HTNO-09	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#4	206.63	159.70	46.93	0.507	0.762	1754	1.00	877	Mitchell	1	73	54	30	31	77	106	51	59	115	159	168	121	168	88	30	773,927	Micro	
HTNO-10	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Dlo_Biolel	240.00	129.49	110.51	0.098	0.305	1677	0.50	839	Pelton	1	45	34	20	18	40	45	23	19	42	65	77	69	77	42	18	369,580	Pico	
HTNO-11	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Mapou	125.89	67.49	58.40	0.137	1.067	1160	2.00	580	Mitchell	2	32	23	13	11	25	26	12	9	22	37	60	51	60	27	9	240,094	Pico	
HTNO-12	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Sainte_Anne	36.07	13.03	23.04	0.506	0.914	2238	1.00	1119	Mitchell	1	46	33	19	17	37	28	14	11	19	39	81	79	81	36	11	314,128	Pico	
HTNO-13	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Zombi	68.58	4.12	64.46	0.105	0.305	695	0.00	0	Pelton	1	29	22	13	11	27	31	16	15	31	45	50	45	50	28	11	247,728	Pico	
HTNO-14	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#5	464.44	315.62	148.82	0.283	0.457	1419	0.75	709	Pelton	1	153	117	66	65	168	229	121	148	253	316	321	234	321	185	65	1,618,614	Mini	
HTNP-01	Nippes	Grande_Riviere_de_Nippes_#1	60.00	9.90	50.10	7.381	1.372	330	0.00	0	Francis	3	2497	2412	2263	2608	2608	2608	2627	2608	2608	2608	2608	2629	2779	2566	2263	22,480,002	Macro	
HTNP-02	Nippes	Grande_Riviere_de_Nippes_#2	150.00	89.43	60.57	7.000	1.372	378	0.00	0	Francis	3	2478	2363	2052	2686	3066	2870	2401	3125	3066	3066	3066	2615	3268	2776	2052	24,318,130	Macro	
HTNP-03	Nippes	Riviere_Charlier	96.87	20.02	76.85	0.229	0.533	2847	0.75	1424	Mitchell	1	44	37	25	37	46	42	27	66	82	121	104	62	121	59	25	517,028	Micro	
HTNP-04	Nippes	Riviere_des_Barraderes	25.08	18.75	6.33	1.902	1.372	603	2.00	302	Kaplan	2	57	48	31	41	72	58	40	55	67	91	91	59	91	60	31	523,443	Micro	
HTNP-05	Nippes	Riviere_Saut_du_Baril	130.61	19.70	110.91	0.221	0.457	3197	0.75	1599	Pelton	2	83	71	51	68	84	77	52	104	125	173	164	106	175	98	51	857,903	Micro	
HTOT-01	Ouest	Etang_de_Miragoane	14.42	0.66	13.76	0.723	1.067	1943	0.00	0	Mitchell	1	60	59	58	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	63	70	67	58	585,077	Micro	
HTOT-02	Ouest	Ravine_Donyen	421.47	298.15	123.32	0.612	0.762	2459	1.50	1230	Pelton	1	202	179	127	216	289	396	338</											

SITE ID	SITE DEPARTEMENT	SITE NAME	DAM W.S. EL. (m)	POWER HOUSE T.W. EL. (m)	GROSS HEAD (m)	TURBINE FLOW (cms)	PENSTOCK DIAMETER (m)	PENSTOCK LENGTH (m)	CANAL WIDTH (m)	CANAL LENGTH (m)	TURBINE TYPE	AMOUNT OF TURBINES	JANUARY POWER (KW)	FEBRUARY POWER (KW)	MARCH POWER (KW)	APRIL POWER (KW)	MAY POWER (KW)	JUNE POWER (KW)	JULY POWER (KW)	AUGUST POWER (KW)	SEPTEMBER POWER (KW)	OCTOBER POWER (KW)	NOVEMBER POWER (KW)	DECEMBER POWER (KW)	MAXIMUM POWER (KW)	AVERAGE POWER (KW)	MINIMUM POWER (KW)	YEARLY ENERGY PRODUCTION (KWH)	SITE CLASSIFICATION	
HTOT-20	Ouest	Ravine_Eau_Fatiguee	945.48	638.06	307.42	0.177	0.305	1346	0.75	673	Pelton	1	242	231	191	250	309	327	276	334	380	398	353	297	398	301	191	2,636,379	Mini	
HTOT-21	Ouest	Riviere_Matheux	230.97	144.97	86.00	2.043	1.067	2669	2.00	1335	Mitchell	1	304	305	229	588	784	895	769	1030	1145	1145	802	443	1146	707	229	6,196,427	Small	
HTOT-22	Ouest	Riviere_Matheux_Hilaire	729.66	236.35	493.31	0.570	0.610	5421	1.00	2711	Pelton	1	707	628	426	787	1251	1570	1331	1894	2148	2148	1632	1046	2148	1305	426	11,433,999	Macro	
HTOT-23	Ouest	Riviere_Momance_#1	160.77	99.77	61.00	6.533	2.134	6704	3.50	3352	Francis	2	771	867	819	2275	2790	2715	2299	2790	2790	2790	1998	1134	2977	2072	771	18,151,407	Macro	
HTOT-24	Ouest	Riviere_Momance_#2	396.51	232.89	163.62	4.420	1.524	7537	3.00	3768	Pelton	2	1639	1652	1457	3104	4135	4079	3537	4765	5058	5095	3622	2249	5179	3407	1457	29,849,592	Macro	
HTOT-25	Ouest	Riviere_Momance_#3	708.27	585.74	122.53	0.909	0.762	2605	1.50	1302	Pelton	2	310	278	219	333	510	599	491	706	797	814	610	434	827	515	219	4,512,061	Small	
HTOT-26	Ouest	Riviere_Plonzac	600.00	427.99	172.01	0.142	0.381	3566	0.75	1783	Pelton	1	40	34	25	63	85	50	34	94	172	178	124	66	178	82	25	718,589	Micro	
HTOT-27	Ouest	Riviere_Redoute	463.17	405.21	57.96	0.697	0.762	1148	1.25	574	Mitchell	1	129	122	98	159	189	200	169	238	275	287	231	174	287	191	98	1,671,761	Mini	
HTOT-28	Ouest	Riviere_Soliete	503.26	301.88	201.38	1.204	0.914	3294	1.75	1647	Pelton	1	425	287	166	176	352	549	257	674	1384	1558	1166	727	1558	660	166	5,777,607	Small	
HTOT-29	Ouest	Riviere_Amazones_#2	482.74	408.50	74.24	0.740	0.762	1888	1.50	944	Francis	2	154	109	60	108	251	265	210	402	402	402	402	250	425	256	60	2,240,510	Mini	
HTOT-30	Ouest	Riviere_Grise_#1	350.00	259.73	90.27	4.216	1.372	2558	3.00	1279	Francis	2	1362	1384	1229	2411	2623	2669	2190	2623	2623	2623	2520	1685	2798	2189	1229	19,176,696	Macro	
HTOT-31	Ouest	Riviere_Grise_#2	400.00	352.08	47.92	4.525	1.067	284	0.00	0	Francis	1	686	696	611	1349	1475	1444	1261	1476	1475	1475	1405	910	1476	1204	611	10,550,029	Macro	
HTOT-32	Ouest	Riviere_Grise_#3	450.00	400.81	49.19	3.369	0.914	243	0.00	0	Francis	1	720	718	644	1088	1119	1117	1037	1119	1119	1119	1117	893	1120	994	644	8,710,227	Small	
HTSD-01	Sud	Ravine_du_Sud	315.77	229.96	85.81	3.944	1.372	3978	0.00	0	Francis	2	1242	1125	643	1559	2408	1930	1476	2094	2434	2408	2408	890	2569	1778	643	15,571,163	Macro	
HTSD-02	Sud	Riviere_Acul	222.94	157.56	65.38	3.874	1.524	3231	0.00	0	Francis	2	976	844	457	1178	1796	1400	1087	1515	1829	1796	1796	632	1914	1321	457	11,575,531	Macro	
HTSD-03	Sud	Riviere_Cavaillon	180.09	117.54	62.55	1.006	1.219	2687	1.50	1344	Francis	2	308	256	130	179	499	343	209	299	463	499	499	428	528	353	130	3,090,235	Mini	
HTSD-04	Sud	Riviere_Cavaillon_(existing)	294.50	183.50	116.00	2.610	0.914	925	1.80	560	Francis	3	890	835	599	772	1267	1245	898	952	1189	2121	2141	1223	2281	1194	599	10,458,148	Macro	
HTSD-05	Sud	Riviere_Cotes_de_Fer	90.00	24.78	65.22	0.326	0.533	1363	0.75	681	Francis	1	153	152	148	154	154	154	151	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	153	148	1,342,758	Mini
HTSD-06	Sud	Riviere_des_Anglais_#1	105.45	65.00	40.45	3.340	1.524	2864	2.50	1432	Francis	2	586	538	289	572	944	749	470	679	922	944	944	694	1007	717	289	6,284,839	Small	
HTSD-07	Sud	Riviere_des_Anglais_#2	206.55	106.71	99.84	1.742	1.067	3744	2.00	1872	Francis	2	778	697	372	636	1228	955	596	805	1161	1228	1228	1014	1308	921	372	8,071,174	Small	
HTSD-08	Sud	Riviere_Mombin	161.97	106.99	54.98	0.543	0.610	869	1.25	434	Mitchell	1	66	49	27	36	109	80	41	89	125	204	198	98	204	95	27	832,452	Micro	
HTSD-09	Sud	Riviere_Mulet	237.38	119.37	118.01	0.614	0.762	2313	1.25	1156	Pelton	1	242	186	107	186	420	276	159	251	349	569	569	267	569	302	107	2,646,059	Mini	
HTSD-10	Sud	Riviere_Port_a_Piment	127.00	42.00	85.00	1.418	1.067	4413	1.50	2206	Francis	2	525	472	247	536	859	666	412	621	851	859	859	528	916	643	247	5,635,626	Small	
HTSD-11	Sud	Riviere_Millionaire	102.00	30.00	72.00	0.787	0.914	3432	1.50	1716	Pelton	2	163	126	76	99	236	187	105	220	291	432	419	228	437	219	76	1,914,782	Mini	
HTSE-01	Sud-Est	Petite_Riviere_de_Jacmel_#1	77.94	7.01	70.93	0.269	0.533	1932	1.00	966	Pelton	1	33	26	18	32	81	34	17	70	111	143	96	54	143	62	17	542,424	Micro	
HTSE-02	Sud-Est	Petite_Riviere_de_Jacmel_#2	218.52	110.03	108.49	0.237	0.457	1181	0.75	590	Pelton	1	45	35	25	42	110	46	25	97	154	199	132	73	199	85	25	745,677	Micro	
HTSE-03	Sud-Est	Riviere_Amazones_#1	263.58	219.19	44.39	1.282	1.067	3164	2.00	1582	Francis	2	161	118	69	133	268	260	195	398	398	398	398	254	421	259	69	2,273,047	Mini	
HTSE-04	Sud-Est	Riviere_Panide	519.98	164.77	355.21	0.295	0.457	3425	0.75	1713	Pelton	1	192	141	89	132	312	424	288	545	701	795	550	328	795	385	89	3,369,803	Mini	
HTSE-05	Sud-Est	Riviere_Bainet_#1	165.56	85.71	79.85	3.091	1.524	6943	0.00	0	Francis	2	691	556	383	940	1443	1164	890	1726	1726	1726	1726	1052	1841	1182	383	10,351,643	Macro	
HTSE-06	Sud-Est	Riviere_Bainet_#2	211.89	164.03	47.86	2.832	1.524	3744	0.00	0	Francis	2	378	296	194	459	744	629	470	1045	983	983	983	587	1049	649	194	5,688,155	Small	
HTSE-07	Sud-Est	Ravine_Perduline	920.00	59.32	860.68	0.900	0.610	7221	0.00	0	Pelton	2	1354	1074	731	1325	3345	3473	2105	3400	4796	5890	3440	2137	5966	2824	731	24,740,616	Macro	
HTSE-08	Sud-Est	Riviere_Dlo_Gene	56.21	10.85	45.36	0.105	0.381	2206	0.50	1103	Pelton	1	8	6	5	9	21	9	4	13	24	33	23	13	33	15	4	127,442	Pico	
HTSE-09	Sud-Est	Riviere_Gaillard	222.64	107.37	115.27	0.127	0.381	1650	0.50	825	Pelton	1	26	20	15	24	49	23	11	48	81	113	76	42	113	46	11	402,928	Pico	
HTSE-10	Sud-Est	Riviere_Gaillard_(existing)	208.95	128.79	80.16	1.071	0.762	1100	0.00	0	Pelton	1	308	248	193	207	467	269	193	396	508	637	479	384	637	366	193	3,206,625	Mini	
HTSE-11	Sud-Est	Riviere_Jacmel_Bras_Droit	130.00	79.61	50.39	0.971	0.914	3157	1.50	1578	Francis	1	192	164	137	235	335	289	174	335	335	335	335	279	335	270	137	2,363,199	Mini	
HTSE-12	Sud-Est	Riviere_Jacmel_Bras_Gauche	120.00	59.80	60.20	1.673	1.067	1628	0.00	0	Francis	1	309	252	200	479	746	606	383	746	746	746	746	485	747	555	200	4,860,824	Small	
HTSE-13	Sud-Est	Riviere_la_Gosseline	150.00	89.52	60.48	1.650	1.219	3313	0.00	0	Mitchell	1	176	151	128	228	418	255	148	436	647	699	502	267	699	346	128	3,032,399	Mini	
HTSE-14	Sud-Est	Riviere_Linet_#1	99.93	39.76	60.17	1.347	1.067	2535	1.75	1268	Mitchell	2	114	86	58	104	264	221	106	340	430	563	346	198	563	247	58	2,161,099	Mini	
HTSE-15	Sud-Est	Riviere_Linet_#2	235.07	189.81	45.26	1.185	0.914	1751	1.50	875	Mitchell	2	81	60	39	62	166	166	106	241	280	351	236	140	351	167	39	1,458,959	Mini	
HTSE-16	Sud-Est	Riviere_Madame_Louis	180.00	9.26	170.74	0.248	0.533	5594	0.75	2797	Pelton	1	98	81	64	87	184	118	72	202	272	317	235	146	317	160	64	1,405,786	Mini	
HTSE-17	Sud-Est	Riviere_des_Plantils	120.00	79.29	40.71	1.859	1.219	1990	2.00	995	Mitchell	2	105	91	73	178	322	285	160	306	426	521	300	167	521	254	73	2,227,304	Mini	
HTSE-18	Sud-Est	Riviere_Pichon	847.78	118.66	729.12	0.724	0.610	5031	1.50	2515	Pelton	2	1010	744	466	572	1830	2395	1075	2201	3785	4031	2580	1633	4098	1907	466	16,707,299	Macro	
HTSE-19	Sud-Est	Riviere_Ti_Letan	327.69	159.16	168.53	0.770	0.762	3939	1.50	1970	Pelton	1	236	176	115	189	479	419	213	673	821	974	691	394	974	462	115	4,043,199	Mini	
HTSE-20	Sud-Est	Riviere_Zoranger	318.47	207.89	110.58	0.827	0.762	2571	0.00	0	Pelton	2	188	144	95	143	348	359	256	516	585	679	516	300	683	352	95	3,083,415	Mini	
HTSE-21	Sud-Est	Ravine_Loquette	696.82	138.03	558.79	0.368	0.457	4229	1.00	2114	Pelton	1	388	288	179	280	763	964	648	1009	1361	1529	1084	648	1529	781	179	6,838,359	Small	
HTSE-22	Sud-Est	Riviere_Blanche_Marigot																												

SITE ID	SITE DEPARTEMENT	SITE NAME	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
HTAR-01	Artibonite	Deluge-Lanzac_(existing)	72°42'19.819"W	18°58'48.613"N
HTAR-02	Artibonite	Drouet_(existing)	72°35'38.972"W	19°8'48.207"N
HTAR-03	Artibonite	EDH_TR-78	72°35'51.834"W	19°40'18.516"N
HTAR-04	Artibonite	Ravine_Montas	72°15'48.663"W	18°56'43.207"N
HTAR-05	Artibonite	Riviere_Blanche	72°17'32.240"W	18°58'2.845"N
HTAR-06	Artibonite	Riviere_Boucan_Fete	72°26'16.113"W	18°58'28.123"N
HTAR-07	Artibonite	Riviere_Bouillie_#1	72°28'21.060"W	19°2'8.449"N
HTAR-08	Artibonite	Riviere_Bouillie_#2	72°29'20.698"W	19°1'27.825"N
HTAR-09	Artibonite	Riviere_Bouillie_#3	72°29'52.734"W	19°1'52.651"N
HTAR-10	Artibonite	Riviere_Cabeuil	72°27'9.343"W	19°13'11.469"N
HTAR-11	Artibonite	Riviere_Deco	72°19'57.372"W	18°54'31.890"N
HTAR-12	Artibonite	Riviere_Ennery	72°30'16.961"W	19°30'43.627"N
HTAR-13	Artibonite	Riviere_Estere_#1	72°26'18.932"W	19°7'34.266"N
HTAR-14	Artibonite	Riviere_Estere_#2	72°24'5.467"W	19°6'49.323"N
HTAR-15	Artibonite	Riviere_Monorouge	72°22'49.594"W	19°8'5.460"N
HTAR-16	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouis_#1	72°32'19.807"W	18°58'8.181"N
HTAR-17	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouis_#2	72°34'9.942"W	18°58'1.236"N
HTAR-18	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouis_#3	72°36'23.719"W	18°58'29.600"N
HTAR-19	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouis_#4	72°34'12.402"W	18°58'5.234"N
HTAR-20	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouis_#5	72°34'38.131"W	18°58'3.877"N
HTAR-21	Artibonite	Riviere_Montrouis_#6	72°35'24.131"W	18°58'11.799"N
HTAR-22	Artibonite	Riviere_Mory	72°23'11.906"W	18°57'25.411"N
HTAR-23	Artibonite	Riviere_Roche	72°21'44.642"W	19°1'3.597"N
HTAR-24	Artibonite	Riviere_Tapion_#1	72°33'14.988"W	19°4'7.895"N
HTAR-25	Artibonite	Riviere_Tapion_#2	72°33'23.026"W	19°2'48.284"N
HTAR-26	Centre	Riviere_Rio_Belle	72°19'52.654"W	19°17'7.400"N
HTAR-27	Artibonite	EDH_ART-1	72°26'37.747"W	19°3'49.512"N
HTAR-28	Artibonite	EDH_ART-2	72°18'24.739"W	18°55'49.353"N
HTAR-29	Artibonite	Riviere_Zepelin	72°24'39.852"W	18°58'22.697"N
HTCT-01	Centre	EDH_ART-4C	72°5'41.444"W	18°52'22.696"N
HTCT-02	Centre	EDH_Peligre_(existing)	72°2'23.084"W	18°54'4.811"N
HTCT-03	Centre	EDH_Dos_Bocas	71°53'8.082"W	18°55'57.258"N
HTCT-04	Centre	EDH_GU-1	71°52'6.830"W	18°58'55.845"N
HTCT-05	Centre	Onde_Verde_(existing)	71°47'23.407"W	18°49'40.453"N
HTCT-06	Centre	Ravine_Trou_Enfer	72°8'36.104"W	18°58'27.923"N
HTCT-07	Centre	Riviere_Abrio	72°6'48.977"W	19°6'55.707"N
HTCT-08	Centre	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#1	72°8'59.388"W	18°55'45.067"N
HTCT-09	Centre	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#2	72°11'58.095"W	18°58'11.552"N
HTCT-10	Centre	Riviere_Boucan_Carre_#3	72°12'6.532"W	18°59'3.759"N
HTCT-11	Centre	Riviere_Cabourette	71°45'53.904"W	18°43'47.766"N
HTCT-12	Centre	Riviere_de_Lascaobas	71°52'26.734"W	18°49'24.900"N
HTCT-13	Centre	Riviere_de_Thomonde	72°2'22.436"W	18°59'46.682"N
HTCT-14	Centre	Riviere_des_Capucins	72°12'30.986"W	18°54'16.258"N
HTCT-15	Centre	Riviere_Dos_Roye	71°47'57.005"W	18°44'15.886"N
HTCT-16	Centre	Riviere_Fond_Bleu_#1	72°12'57.966"W	19°9'5.798"N
HTCT-17	Centre	Riviere_Fond_Bleu_#2	72°13'4.512"W	19°7'41.417"N
HTCT-18	Centre	Riviere_Fond_Gras	72°14'32.164"W	19°9'57.678"N
HTCT-19	Centre	Riviere_Fraicheur	71°55'39.073"W	18°48'58.697"N
HTCT-20	Centre	Riviere_Grand_Saut	72°15'8.137"W	18°48'1.637"N
HTCT-21	Centre	Riviere_Hinquite	72°3'42.989"W	19°5'16.169"N
HTCT-22	Centre	Riviere_la_Theme_#1	72°6'31.164"W	18°49'41.190"N
HTCT-23	Centre	Riviere_la_Theme_#2	72°12'29.014"W	18°48'35.070"N
HTCT-24	Centre	Riviere_Layaye	71°49'3.185"W	18°44'29.241"N
HTCT-25	Centre	Riviere_Goyave	72°1'20.366"W	19°2'0.339"N
HTCT-26	Centre	Riviere_Rio_Frio	72°9'34.605"W	19°7'22.775"N
HTCT-27	Centre	Riviere_Roche_Blanche	71°50'40.184"W	18°50'2.317"N
HTCT-28	Centre	Riviere_Roche_Plate	71°48'8.025"W	18°49'28.715"N
HTCT-29	Centre	Riviere_Samana	71°58'47.855"W	19°13'16.391"N

SITE ID	SITE DEPARTEMENT	SITE NAME	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
HTCT-30	Centre	Riviere_Senador	71°53'32.850"W	18°49'44.055"N
HTCT-31	Centre	Riviere_Locianne	71°44'47.869"W	19°7'36.447"N
HTGA-01	Grande Anse	Grande_Anse_#1	74°6'59.768"W	18°37'8.770"N
HTGA-02	Grande Anse	Grande_Anse_#2	74°15'39.869"W	18°32'52.364"N
HTGA-03	Grande Anse	Grande_Anse_#3	74°20'13.787"W	18°28'22.612"N
HTGA-04	Grande Anse	Grande_Anse_#4	74°21'56.364"W	18°25'36.840"N
HTGA-05	Grande Anse	Riviere_de_la_Voldroque	74°7'5.945"W	18°32'17.578"N
HTGA-06	Grande Anse	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#1	74°0'45.188"W	18°33'46.672"N
HTGA-07	Grande Anse	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#2	74°2'19.317"W	18°30'18.816"N
HTGA-08	Grande Anse	Riviere_des_Roseaux_#3	74°2'16.305"W	18°27'12.666"N
HTGA-09	Grande Anse	Riviere_Glace_#1	73°52'14.416"W	18°27'1.249"N
HTGA-10	Grande Anse	Riviere_Glace_#2	73°53'29.536"W	18°26'15.472"N
HTGA-11	Grande Anse	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#1	74°2'21.142"W	18°27'12.907"N
HTGA-12	Grande Anse	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#2	74°2'21.913"W	18°24'54.670"N
HTGA-13	Grande Anse	Riviere_la_Guinaudee_#3	74°2'16.692"W	18°24'53.838"N
HTND-01	Nord	Grande_Rivine	72°26'13.029"W	18°26'39.078"N
HTND-02	Nord	Petite_Riviere	72°6'42.985"W	19°37'0.191"N
HTND-03	Nord	Riviere_Bouyaha	72°14'57.659"W	19°31'21.056"N
HTND-04	Nord	Riviere_Caracol_(existing)	72°6'52.212"W	19°33'26.459"N
HTND-05	Nord	Riviere_Dore	72°24'44.443"W	19°34'18.161"N
HTND-06	Nord	Riviere_Marmelade	72°24'49.606"W	19°34'16.528"N
HTND-07	Nord	Riviere_Morro_#1	72°33'35.620"W	19°48'59.217"N
HTND-08	Nord	Riviere_Morro_#2	72°33'56.576"W	19°46'43.828"N
HTND-09	Nord	Riviere_Vaseuse	72°14'35.679"W	19°32'42.919"N
HTNE-01	Nord-Est	Grande_Riviere_du_Nord_#1	72°3'58.075"W	19°26'23.201"N
HTNE-02	Nord-Est	Grande_Riviere_du_Nord_#2	72°2'38.852"W	19°25'52.561"N
HTNE-03	Nord-Est	Riviere_Marrion	71°52'9.058"W	19°33'29.270"N
HTNE-04	Nord-Est	Riviere_Louisa	71°48'30.588"W	19°26'57.179"N
HTNE-05	Nord-Est	Riviere_Gens_de_Nantes_#1	71°42'47.752"W	19°28'5.760"N
HTNE-06	Nord-Est	Riviere_Gens_de_Nantes_#2	71°47'17.928"W	19°26'10.114"N
HTNO-01	Nord-Ouest	EDH_TR-28	72°50'18.688"W	19°49'59.208"N
HTNO-02	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_au_Four	72°42'41.572"W	19°52'12.647"N
HTNO-03	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Bon_Temps	72°40'47.823"W	19°49'45.731"N
HTNO-04	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Cap_Rouge	72°40'28.365"W	19°54'17.762"N
HTNO-05	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Dejour	72°45'46.779"W	19°55'51.889"N
HTNO-06	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#1	72°42'20.849"W	19°54'28.253"N
HTNO-07	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#2	72°42'10.412"W	19°51'38.859"N
HTNO-08	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#3	72°41'56.867"W	19°51'15.131"N
HTNO-09	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#4	72°40'33.309"W	19°49'30.875"N
HTNO-10	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Dlo_Biolel	72°41'5.585"W	19°50'8.693"N
HTNO-11	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Mapou	72°41'52.549"W	19°51'14.342"N
HTNO-12	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Sainte_Anne	72°37'4.916"W	19°53'5.050"N
HTNO-13	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_Zombi	72°37'49.933"W	19°53'33.217"N
HTNO-14	Nord-Ouest	Riviere_des_Barres_#5	72°38'20.002"W	19°48'32.200"N
HTNP-01	Nippes	Grande_Riviere_de_Nippes_#1	73°19'23.059"W	18°27'26.764"N
HTNP-02	Nippes	Grande_Riviere_de_Nippes_#2	73°24'27.309"W	18°24'34.939"N
HTNP-03	Nippes	Riviere_Charlier	73°11'18.475"W	18°28'29.781"N
HTNP-04	Nippes	Riviere_des_Barraderes	73°40'27.706"W	18°27'34.368"N
HTNP-05	Nippes	Riviere_Saut_du_Baril	73°17'36.454"W	18°27'49.375"N
HTOT-01	Ouest	Etang_de_Miragoane	73°4'4.282"W	18°26'46.249"N
HTOT-02	Ouest	Ravine_Donyen	72°27'46.218"W	18°50'41.465"N
HTOT-03	Ouest	Ravine_Grande	72°9'0.586"W	18°23'11.499"N
HTOT-04	Ouest	Ravine_Minerve	72°6'17.684"W	18°26'48.308"N
HTOT-05	Ouest	Ravine_Seche_#1	72°0'30.660"W	18°44'21.792"N
HTOT-06	Ouest	Ravine_Seche_#2	71°57'8.880"W	18°42'58.318"N
HTOT-07	Ouest	Riviere_au_Foure_(Momance)	72°26'12.400"W	18°28'47.530"N
HTOT-08	Ouest	Riviere_Auby	72°28'41.945"W	18°52'14.503"N
HTOT-09	Ouest	Riviere_Barret	72°54'59.809"W	18°24'34.395"N

SITE ID	SITE DEPARTEMENT	SITE NAME	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
HTOT-10	Ouest	Riviere_Blanche_Ouest_#1	72°6'59.314"W	18°29'34.885"N
HTOT-11	Ouest	Riviere_Blanche_Ouest_#2	72°6'14.359"W	18°26'46.022"N
HTOT-12	Ouest	Riviere_Boucan_Greffin	72°5'22.371"W	18°26'20.759"N
HTOT-13	Ouest	Riviere_Cazale_#1	72°23'6.683"W	18°47'26.238"N
HTOT-14	Ouest	Riviere_Cazale_#2	72°22'45.719"W	18°48'40.759"N
HTOT-15	Ouest	Riviere_Cazale_#3	72°23'35.883"W	18°49'23.753"N
HTOT-16	Ouest	Riviere_Fauche	72°43'34.171"W	18°24'34.822"N
HTOT-17	Ouest	Riviere_Fond_Parisien_#1	71°58'14.194"W	18°28'34.828"N
HTOT-18	Ouest	Riviere_Fond_Parisien_#2	71°58'14.243"W	18°28'34.808"N
HTOT-19	Ouest	Riviere_Froide	72°24'40.400"W	18°30'41.256"N
HTOT-20	Ouest	Ravine_Eau_Fatiguee	72°14'15.601"W	18°23'5.581"N
HTOT-21	Ouest	Riviere_Matheux	72°31'16.212"W	18°50'44.037"N
HTOT-22	Ouest	Riviere_Matheux_Hilaire	72°31'29.473"W	18°52'0.539"N
HTOT-23	Ouest	Riviere_Momance_#1	72°32'41.496"W	18°28'17.394"N
HTOT-24	Ouest	Riviere_Momance_#2	72°26'2.292"W	18°28'49.595"N
HTOT-25	Ouest	Riviere_Momance_#3	72°21'7.547"W	18°24'3.288"N
HTOT-26	Ouest	Riviere_Plonzac	71°57'12.129"W	18°43'28.355"N
HTOT-27	Ouest	Riviere_Redoute	72°11'13.911"W	18°26'6.647"N
HTOT-28	Ouest	Riviere_Soliete	71°52'53.682"W	18°26'45.419"N
HTOT-29	Ouest	Riviere_Amazones_#2	72°54'24.168"W	18°19'8.073"N
HTOT-30	Ouest	Riviere_Grise_#1	72°10'14.497"W	18°28'27.137"N
HTOT-31	Ouest	Riviere_Grise_#2	72°10'26.933"W	18°26'16.579"N
HTOT-32	Ouest	Riviere_Grise_#3	72°10'1.192"W	18°25'46.821"N
HTSD-01	Sud	Ravine_du_Sud	73°52'12.733"W	18°20'27.655"N
HTSD-02	Sud	Riviere_Acul	73°56'35.349"W	18°15'54.386"N
HTSD-03	Sud	Riviere_Cavaillon	73°49'27.430"W	18°21'22.947"N
HTSD-04	Sud	Riviere_Cavaillon_(existing)	73°50'36.591"W	18°22'9.244"N
HTSD-05	Sud	Riviere_Cotes_de_Fer	73°0'28.136"W	18°12'31.878"N
HTSD-06	Sud	Riviere_des_Anglais_#1	74°10'54.203"W	18°19'53.392"N
HTSD-07	Sud	Riviere_des_Anglais_#2	74°9'24.327"W	18°19'46.756"N
HTSD-08	Sud	Riviere_Mombin	73°33'56.464"W	18°18'47.614"N
HTSD-09	Sud	Riviere_Mulet	73°59'22.896"W	18°13'14.852"N
HTSD-10	Sud	Riviere_Port_a_Piment	74°5'5.061"W	18°16'17.705"N
HTSD-11	Sud	Riviere_Millionaire	73°30'43.970"W	18°17'28.722"N
HTSE-01	Sud-Est	Petite_Riviere_de_Jacmel_#1	72°33'29.278"W	18°13'51.491"N
HTSE-02	Sud-Est	Petite_Riviere_de_Jacmel_#2	72°34'38.897"W	18°14'0.043"N
HTSE-03	Sud-Est	Riviere_Amazones_#1	72°55'48.780"W	18°15'27.835"N
HTSE-04	Sud-Est	Riviere_Panide	72°18'11.985"W	18°15'56.044"N
HTSE-05	Sud-Est	Riviere_Bainet_#1	72°50'53.667"W	18°13'1.996"N
HTSE-06	Sud-Est	Riviere_Bainet_#2	72°54'2.827"W	18°14'25.826"N
HTSE-07	Sud-Est	Ravine_Perdule	72°18'43.633"W	18°14'56.186"N
HTSE-08	Sud-Est	Riviere_Dlo_Gene	72°38'17.660"W	18°11'45.431"N
HTSE-09	Sud-Est	Riviere_Gaillard	72°23'51.278"W	18°15'16.656"N
HTSE-10	Sud-Est	Riviere_Gaillard_(existing)	72°23'57.268"W	18°15'26.947"N
HTSE-11	Sud-Est	Riviere_Jacmel_Bras_Droit	72°33'59.790"W	18°18'4.792"N
HTSE-12	Sud-Est	Riviere_Jacmel_Bras_Gauche	72°35'5.094"W	18°16'34.003"N
HTSE-13	Sud-Est	Riviere_la_Gosseline	72°29'44.171"W	18°18'33.947"N
HTSE-14	Sud-Est	Riviere_Linet_#1	72°47'44.134"W	18°11'39.508"N
HTSE-15	Sud-Est	Riviere_Linet_#2	72°46'26.967"W	18°14'41.936"N
HTSE-16	Sud-Est	Riviere_Madame_Louis	72°40'13.463"W	18°11'27.852"N
HTSE-17	Sud-Est	Riviere_des_Plantils	72°19'9.464"W	18°15'24.776"N
HTSE-18	Sud-Est	Riviere_Pichon	72°1'39.754"W	18°15'38.181"N
HTSE-19	Sud-Est	Riviere_Ti_Letan	72°37'48.955"W	18°17'45.692"N
HTSE-20	Sud-Est	Riviere_Zoranger	72°48'59.202"W	18°16'5.439"N
HTSE-21	Sud-Est	Ravine_Loquette	72°18'9.678"W	18°15'40.973"N
HTSE-22	Sud-Est	Riviere_Blanche_Marigot	72°20'39.561"W	18°17'33.738"N

